

Reflection of 'Subaltern' in Mahatma Gandhi's Autobiography: *The Story of My Experiments with Truth (1927)*

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Abstract

The most influential leader of the Indian independence struggle during British rule was Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi. Gandhi led India to independence via peaceful civil disobedience, and he also served as an inspiration for freedom and civil rights movements around the globe. He is referred to as Bapu, or the "father of nation," and he led India's national struggle from 1919 to 1947. He was a fervent supporter of *Purna Swaraj*, or total independence, and a champion of nonviolence and peace. His message is appealing to all people and has had a significant impact on humanity up to this point. He had a vision of *Swaraj*, which he compared to Rama Rajya, the earthly kingdom of God. This research paper looks at the rhetorical devices used in *The Story of My Experiments with Truth (1927)*, Gandhi's autobiography. Gandhi claims to speak for the concerns of South African and Indian subalterns in British India as he develops his story of identity. Gandhi's autobiography uses derogatory stereotypes to characterize the attitudes of the Indian population regarding hygienic practices, which objectifies them.

Keywords: subaltern, dirt, cleanliness, hygiene, self-identity

Introduction

As a literary form, autobiography tells the tale of one's own life as written or spoken by the autobiographical character. This discourse, which argues that writing ensures the self's existence and continuity, is particularly promising. Through a literary encoding of self-presence, an idealistic hope of self-preservation is produced and framed. As such, the storyline of an autobiographical narrative revolves around the narrator. To put it another way, the narrator of an autobiography is a part of the story, not an outsider. She or he uses the "I", a literary device to tell and advance his or her story. It is important to emphasize that reading Gandhi's autobiography is similar to reading a textbook on philosophy. The text's

discussion seems more like a passage taken from one of Descartes', Hume's, Kierkegaard's, Locke's, or Karl Marx's writings.

Gandhi's story is essentially a thoughtful account of commands and limitations presented via the lens of moral discipline and self-imposed fasting. However, the book also integrates the story of its "other" while telling the protagonist's story. Gandhi's use of the Indian subaltern masses as a palimpsest to write down his identity is evident in his autobiography. He illustrates how his identity contrasts sharply with the identities of the Indian subaltern groups. Among other things, he employs the cliché of "dirt" to measure his distinction from the majority of Indians. Therefore, "dirt" becomes the conceptual trajectory that he uses to apply his identity-construction story. For instance, his book has several complaints against the unhygienic actions of the Indian underclass. Throughout his story, he laments the majority of Indians' unwillingness to practice basic environmental sanitation.

In his autobiography, He complains that "It was too much for people to bestir themselves to keep their surroundings clean" (p. 205). According to him, "the Indian was slovenly in his habits and did not keep his house and surroundings clean" (p. 205). The idea is that, although Gandhi shares Indian ancestry with the subalterns in his book, his status as an educated lawyer sets him apart from them.

Gandhi must have been aware of his advantage over other Indian groups, both in South Africa and India, as a learned member of the elite and a reformer. Gandhi, for the most part, is a strong proponent of a more universal humanity that transcends race and religion. Thus, his desire to mold the Indian masses into his own likeness fires him. But he fails miserably in this endeavor, particularly when it comes to changing the general Indian populace's understanding of aesthetics. Thus, he sees himself in the guise of a rejected "reformer" in the narrative who gets nothing from his society but "opposition, abhorrence and even mortal persecution" (p. 206).

He complains endlessly about the collective will of the subalterns to reject positive change in matters of hygiene and cleanliness. In this regard, he notes, "Sanitation was a difficult affair. The people were not prepared to do anything themselves. Even the field labourers were not ready to do their own scavenging" (p. 381). In the autobiography, *The Story of My Experiments with Truth*, it is repeatedly witnessed this pattern of complaint about environmental and hygienic negligence (p. 165, p. 166, p. 212, p. 352, p. 381, p. 386). Gandhi's excessive concern with "dirt" and "cleanliness" is a direct result of his privileged middle-class mindset. Gandhi does not intend to alienate the subalterns from their shared social milieu, but he is eager to emphasize the differences between himself and them. In this sense, he cares more about dominance than exclusion. As it was discussed above, Gandhi is able to label and categorize the subalterns as "dirty," "abnormal," "retrogressive," and "rigid" due to the unbalanced power dynamics that exist between him and them.

Conclusion

The present paper has looked at Gandhi's re-presentation of the voiceless underclass, who have a prominent place in his story. It has observed how the text uses unfavorable tropes to represent this marginalized group. It "thingifies" them through the social hierarchies such as clean/dirty, obedient/revolting, normative/transgressive, liberal/conservative, and rich/poor. There is unquestionably a hierarchical power structure at work in the text. Gandhi is positioned at the top of the power pyramid in this configuration, with the subalterns at the bottom. Gandhi is therefore given a place at the center of the narrative consciousness of the book. Gandhi succeeds in minimizing the subalterns' unity-in-difference, their diversity, and their particularity as human subjects. At the same time, he projects himself as clean,

dutiful, responsible and sociable. He has distinguished himself clearly among the subalterns. It is evident that such favourable characterizations of himself as opposed to the negative descriptions of the subalterns provide him with a platform to articulate his preferred identity. Gandhi therefore proves that he is everything the subalterns are not.

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